

WHAT YOU WRITE WHEN YOU WRITE ABOUT TEACHING CREATIVITY: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

QUÉ SE ESCRIBE AL ESCRIBIR SOBRE LA CREATIVIDAD DOCENTE: UNA REVISIÓN
SISTEMÁTICA DE LA LITERATURE

DO QUE SE ESCREVE QUANDO SE ESCREVE SOBRE CRIATIVIDADE DOCENTE: UMA
REVISÃO SISTEMÁTICA DE LITERATURA

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Abstract

This article presents, through a Systematic Literature Review that analyzed a corpus of 70 publications—including journal articles, conference proceedings, and book chapters in Portuguese, Spanish, and English—a panorama of teaching creativity over the past decade and what has been considered indicative of a creative teacher. To address the central question of what it means to be a creative teacher, three secondary questions were defined: the first investigated the concepts of teaching creativity employed; the second analyzed the main convergences and divergences in the definitions of teaching creativity found in the studies; and the third sought to identify research gaps highlighted by the studies. The review revealed a diversity of approaches, methods, and understandings related to teaching creativity, but also highlighted relevant convergences and divergences for future research. There was a general recognition of the importance of creativity in the context of teaching and learning, with an emphasis on its relevance to critical and reflective teacher education.

Keywords: Mathematical Education; Teaching Methods; Creative Teaching; Teacher Characteristics.

Resumen

Este artículo presenta, mediante una Revisión Sistemática de la Literatura que analizó un corpus de 70 publicaciones, incluidos artículos en revistas, actas de congresos y capítulos de libros en

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portugués, español e inglés, un panorama sobre la creatividad docente en la última década y lo que se ha considerado indicativo de un docente creativo. Para responder a la pregunta central sobre qué significa ser un docente creativo, se definieron tres preguntas secundarias: la primera investigó los conceptos de creatividad docente utilizados; la segunda analizó las principales convergencias y divergencias en los conceptos de creatividad docente presentes en los estudios; y la tercera buscó identificar vacíos de investigación señalados por los estudios. La investigación reveló una diversidad de enfoques, métodos y comprensiones relacionados con la creatividad docente, pero también destacó convergencias y divergencias relevantes para investigaciones futuras. Hubo un reconocimiento general de la importancia de la creatividad en el contexto de la enseñanza y el aprendizaje, con énfasis en su relevancia para la formación crítica y reflexiva.

Palabras clave: Educación Matemática; Métodos de enseñanza; Enseñanza creativa; Características docentes.

Resumo

Este artigo traz, por meio de uma Revisão Sistemática de Literatura que analisou um corpus de 70 publicações, incluindo artigos em periódicos e anais de eventos e capítulos de livros em língua portuguesa, espanhola e inglesa, um panorama sobre a criatividade docente na última década e o que tem sido considerado indicativo de um docente criativo. Para responder à pergunta central sobre o que significa ser um docente criativo, foram definidas três questões secundárias: a primeira investigou os conceitos de criatividade docente utilizados; a segunda analisou as principais convergências e divergências nos conceitos de criatividade docente dos estudos; e a terceira buscou identificar lacunas de pesquisa indicadas pelos estudos. A pesquisa revelou uma diversidade de abordagens, métodos e entendimentos relacionados à criatividade docente, mas também destacou convergências e divergências relevantes para futuras pesquisas. Houve um reconhecimento geral da importância da criatividade no contexto do ensino e da aprendizagem, com ênfase em sua relevância para a formação crítica e reflexiva.

Palavras-chave: Educação Matemática; Métodos de ensino; Ensino Criativo; Características docentes.

Introduction

*It is not information that moves the world toward progress;
it is actions based on knowledge and creativity.
(Agüera, 2011, p.23 - translated by the authors)*

The Brazilian population is composed of creative people, and this statement is not merely an impression of those who observe and deal with human behavior, whether as citizens or as mathematics educators in the 21st century. It is also affirmed by one of the great figures of Brazilian education, Darcy Ribeiro, in his work *The Brazilian People*, published in 1995. Ribeiro (2006) highlights the creativity, adaptability, originality, flexibility, and vitality of those who face challenges boldly. That is, for him, being creative is intrinsically linked to being Brazilian.

At the same time, Paulo Freire, considered the patron of Brazilian education, when criticizing the “banking”⁴ A model of teaching argued that it hinders the creativity of both learners and educators (Freire, 1996). In this sense, Freire proposes creativity, closely tied to curiosity, which drives us and makes us "patiently impatient in the face of a world we did not create," yet to which we add something of our own (Freire, 1996, p. 18).

What Freire warned about is still a topic of discussion today. According to Chamberlin *et al.* (2023), when educators intentionally commit to fostering creativity in teaching⁵, the chances of developing this skill in students increase significantly. This is one of the reasons why Basic Education was chosen as the context for this research, since it is at this stage that competencies and skills are developed, and if one of them is creativity, the earlier it is nurtured in the educational context, the better.

Regarding the context of Brazilian education, it is worth noting that Law No. 9.394 of December 20, 1996, the Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação (LDB), although it does not explicitly emphasize the importance of creativity, provides guidelines that can be interpreted as opportunities or incentives for innovative and creative practices in educational processes: (i) Curricular Flexibility, which allows a certain degree of autonomy for educational institutions to develop their curricula, provided they comply with the general guidelines, this makes room for the inclusion of innovative pedagogical practices; (ii) Continuous Teacher Education, which can support more creative and innovative teaching practices; and (iii) Integral Education, which focuses on the full development of the student and can create space for practices that value creativity and innovation as integral parts of the educational process (Brazil, 1996).

Another key regulatory document for structuring Basic Education in Brazil is the Base Nacional Comum Curricular (BNCC), which establishes the knowledge, competencies, and skills expected for students' development throughout basic schooling. Regarding the development of creativity, the document includes the act of creating in several skills: four

⁴ "This 'banking' concept implies, in addition to the interests already mentioned, other aspects that involve a false view of human beings. These aspects are sometimes made explicit, sometimes not, in their practice. It suggests a non-existent dichotomy between humans and the world. Humans are merely in the world, and not with the world and with others. Humans as spectators, not as re-creators of the world." (Freire, 1970, p. 40)

⁵ The authors discuss the teaching of Mathematics, but we understand that the same applies to other fields of knowledge as well.

related to Early Childhood Education (Elo2TS02, Elo3CG01, Elo3CG03, Elo2EF06), nine associated with Elementary Education (EF01GE08, EF02LP02, EF12EF01, EF15AR11, EF35LP25, EF67LP30, EF69AR23, EF89LP35, EF89LP36), and three from High School (EM13LP18, EM13LP54, EM13LGG602).⁶

The skills intended for Early Childhood Education, for instance, aim to stimulate the development of creativity, expression, and sensory perception. They include sound and musical exploration, manipulation of varied materials, expression of feelings and emotions through the body, and the creation and oral narration of stories. These activities foster auditory perception, fine motor coordination, body awareness, and language skills. Through such practices, the goal is to encourage children's creative expression in various forms and contexts.

In Elementary Education, the skills are divided between Early and Final Years, reflecting expectations appropriate for each stage. In the Early Years, the focus is on the development of basic language skills, environmental awareness, cultural appreciation, and physical expression. In the Final Years, the skills aim to enhance critical thinking, artistic expression, and cultural awareness, encouraging autonomy and complexity. Both sets aim to promote creativity through cultural participation and the appreciation of both individual and collective expression.

For High School, the skills emphasize the integration of technology, creativity, artistic appreciation, and personal expression. Students are encouraged to express their ideas and feelings through different media, to participate in artistic and cultural manifestations, and to use digital tools.

Even if Brazilian legislation does not yet explicitly emphasize creativity as a strategic element in the teaching and learning context, beyond what has already been outlined in a scattered way in the BNCC (Oliveira; Boscaroli; Vertuan, 2025), there are still records showing that creativity has been the focus of the Brazilian Ministry of Education⁷ itself. In 2015, the Ministry launched the public call "Innovation and Creativity in Basic Education," which received 690 submissions of educational experiences from all regions of Brazil. The initiative aimed to identify, recognize, and map educational actions that diverged from the traditional teaching model to disseminate them (Ministério da Educação - MEC, 2015).

⁶ To learn about the related skills, visit <http://basenacionalcomum.mec.gov.br/>

⁷ Dilma Rousseff's government (2011–2016).

The traditional or conventional teaching model, as we understand it, is strongly rooted in practices and structures built over time, but which no longer meet the demands of society. In this model, the teacher is the main source of knowledge and authority, expository lectures without dialogue prevail, and assessments focus on testing the memorization of information. Moreover, there is limited technological integration and a curriculum that is not adapted to the specific needs of students or the characteristics of their communities (Antelo, 2002; Cavalcante, 2020).

Still, regarding the public call for "Innovation and Creativity in Basic Education," 178 educational institutions stood out, allowing for an initial overview of educational innovation in Brazil. The data indicated actions distributed across the five regions of the country, reflecting the population distribution: 50.8% in the Southeast, 21.9% in the Northeast, 13.7% in the South, 8.7% in the Center-West, and 7.6% in the North (MEC, 2015). This initiative aimed to culminate in the Map of Innovation and Creativity in Basic Education⁸, which was indeed created at the time, but the project was not carried forward⁹.

Creativity in the school environment is essential for the holistic development of students and has increasingly been incorporated into complex contexts. On this topic, Martínez (2002) emphasizes the importance of the school environment, stating that to effectively contribute to the development of creativity, it is necessary to work on at least three interconnected dimensions: the development of students' creativity, of educators' creativity, and of the school itself as an organizational climate. Focusing on the teacher, López Martínez (2008, p.74) states:

The educator is the leader, facilitator, and mediator who enables the student and the various elements that foster the development of creativity to come together in the educational space. There is general agreement that the educator must be creative or, at the very least, use creative methods and techniques. (translated by the authors).

Researchers have proposed several dimensions for the development of creativity in the teaching context. For instance, López Martínez (2008) highlights the triad of educator, student, and classroom environment; Lin (2011) proposes a categorization of the relationship between creativity, teaching, and learning that can be understood through

⁸ https://simec.mec.gov.br/educriativa/mapa_questionario.php

⁹ The government website <http://criatividade.mec.gov.br/> is currently offline.

three lenses: teaching for creativity, teaching creatively, and fostering creative learning; and Soh (2017), in turn, focuses on specific aspects of teacher behavior that can foster creativity. In this regard, he identifies three central elements: social modeling, reinforcement, and classroom ecology.

From the aforementioned authors, we observe three approaches that converge in establishing the necessary interrelationship between teacher and student. However, this goes beyond merely strengthening the academic relationship, as there is a fundamental aspect that must be immediately considered: “sometimes, the simplicity and trivialization of the very concept [of creativity] become barriers to effective work aimed at achieving truly meaningful results” (Martínez, 2002, p. 190).

Martínez (2002) points out that one of the main barriers to the development of student creativity is the lack of knowledge on the part of educators [teachers] regarding what to develop and how to do so. That said, it becomes evident to us, the authors, that there is a need for research on teaching creativity, starting with an understanding of what has in fact been investigated in this context. This gives rise to the central question: What is written when writing about teaching creativity?

From this main question, we developed the following secondary questions to guide the data analysis: What does it mean to be a creative teacher? (SQ1) What concepts of teaching creativity are used by researchers reflecting on this topic? (SQ2) And, what are the main convergences and divergences regarding the concepts of teaching creativity identified in these studies? (SQ3). Addressing these questions—even at a preliminary level—makes it possible to invent the concepts of teaching creativity through a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) with a predominantly qualitative focus.

Assuming creativity as a sociocultural process, Prado, Alencar, and Fleith (2016) define it as a multifaceted, multidimensional phenomenon influenced by a range of aspects that interact in its expression. According to them, intrapersonal factors encompass cognitive and affective skills and personality traits, while external aspects involve the environment, culture, and historical context.

The combination of these intra- and interpersonal (external) factors can foster the emergence and appreciation of innovative ideas, as well as reinforce individual characteristics related to creativity (Prado; Alencar; Fleith, 2016). This awareness is not new

and appeared in the studies of Guilford (1973), who, when addressing the characteristics of creativity, presented a list of 20 questions directed at teachers—the first being: “Do you really care about teaching?”

From this and the other 19 questions, it is possible to infer the author’s concept of teaching creativity. For him, a creative teacher sees teaching as a way of life, not merely a job. They constantly reinvent themselves, exploring new methods, materials, and ideas—even beyond their area of expertise. They value each student, avoid labels and comparisons, and remain open to innovative approaches, even in contemporary areas. Rather than strictly following the curriculum, they enrich their lessons with diverse resources, encourage free expression, and address challenging topics. Additionally, they create an environment conducive to learning, actively engage with the community, and continuously seek new knowledge, reflecting deeply on the purpose of education (Guilford, 1973).

We also highlight the perspective of Wechsler (2002), who describes a creative teacher as someone open to new experiences, bold, curious, self-sufficient, and passionate about their work, approaching teaching with idealism and enthusiasm, acting as a facilitator, and breaking away from the molds of what is considered conventional education.

This view aligns with that of Martínez (2002), for whom the school environment is crucial in shaping the personal characteristics that influence an individual’s creative capacity. This makes evident the importance of well-planned educational strategies aimed at enhancing these individual traits and expanding the creative expression of learners.

Although the reflections are not limited to the works of Guilford (1973), Wechsler (2002), and Martínez (2002), they already reveal a clear interaction between teaching practice and aspects such as intentional creativity, motivation, and the socio-historical context. Based on these reflections and considering the temporal window of the last decade, it becomes possible to conceive what is written when writing about teaching creativity. This will be explored in the following sections, detailing the methodology used in this research, the development of the review, and finally, the conclusions, which present the answers and reflections reached throughout the study.

Methodological Approach

In this research, a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was chosen due to its methodological robustness. According to Dermeval, Coelho, and Bittencourt (2020), this approach identifies and evaluates studies published on a specific issue with the goal of consolidating knowledge. Systematic reviews require a predefined search strategy, considering a specific time frame, pre-established keywords, and clear criteria for the inclusion and exclusion of works or publications. The protocol used here is based on Dermeval, Coelho, and Bittencourt (2020), whose general guidelines for conducting each stage of the protocol are: research question, study search and selection process, data extraction, and data synthesis and analysis.

Once the research questions were defined, the study search and selection process involved choosing the sources of information. In this case, the selected databases were CAPES Journals, Google Scholar, and ERIC – Education Resources Information Center.

In the search and selection process, keywords directly related to the main question were employed, along with their variations: “criatividade” (creativity), “docente” (teacher), “professor” (teacher), “educador” (educator), including their respective feminine and plural forms. The search strings ¹⁰They were adapted according to the platform and the language. On ERIC, for example, combinations such as "Creatividad" AND "Docente" or "Creativity" AND "Teachers" were used. On Google Scholar, the focus was on titles containing expressions such as "Creatividad" and "Profesor" or "Creativity" and "Teachers". A similar approach was adopted for the CAPES Journals database.

Before defining the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the time frame for the search was established. For this, the historical milestone of 2015 was considered—the year in which the national public call for “Innovation and Creativity in Basic Education” took place. Given the symbolic significance of nearly a decade since this event in Brazilian Basic Education, it was decided to limit the publications to the last ten years, covering the period from January 2013 to May 2023.

¹⁰ **Eric** - title: "Creatividad" AND "Docente" OR "Creatividad AND "Profesor" OR "Creatividad AND "Maestro". **Google Scholar** - allintitle: “Creatividad” “Profesor” OR “Profesores” OR “Profesora” OR “Profesoras” OR “Maestro” OR “Maestros” OR “Maestra” OR “Maestras” OR “Docente” OR “Docentes”. **Capex** - allintitle: “Creatividad” AND “Profesor” OR “Profesores” OR “Profesora” OR “Profesoras” OR “Maestro” OR “Maestros” OR “Maestra” OR “Maestras” OR “Docente” OR “Docentes”. **Eric** - title: "Creativity" AND "Teachers" OR "Creativity" AND "Educators". **Google Scholar** - allintitle: "Creativity AND Teachers" OR "Creativity AND Educators". **Capex** - allintitle: “Creativity AND Teachers” OR “Creativity AND Educators”.

In an initial data survey, the following quantities were found: on Google Scholar (GS), 318 publications were identified in Portuguese, 30 in English, and 325 in Spanish. On ERIC (E), no publications were found in Portuguese or Spanish, while 115 were identified in English. On the CAPES platform (C), we found 58 publications in Portuguese, 57 in English, and 116 in Spanish, resulting in a total of 376 publications in Portuguese, 202 in English, and 441 in Spanish. The inclusion criteria defined were: theoretical or empirical studies focused on teaching creativity, published in Portuguese, English, or Spanish, and available in full for download. Based on these criteria, 153 publications in Portuguese, 58 in English, and 49 in Spanish were selected.

The following exclusion criteria were established: systematic review or mapping studies; theoretical or empirical studies focused on student creativity or on future teachers; studies related to teacher insubordination or creativity in higher education; duplicate studies; and derivative studies that did not present new data. After this filtering process, 43 publications in Portuguese remained (9 from conference proceedings, 28 from journals, and 4 book chapters), 17 in English (all journal articles), and 12 in Spanish (2 from conference proceedings, 8 from journals, and 2 book chapters), resulting in a corpus of 70 publications (Table 1).

Table 1 – References of the publications included in the corpus for analysis

AE1-Sánchez (2017)	AR14-Marques & Silva (2013)	AR38-Al-Nouh, Abdul-Kareem & Taqi (2014)
AE2-Albuquerque (2021)	AR15-Martins & Bertoldo (2013)	AR40-Anderson et al. (2022)
AE3-Cruz (2021)	AR16-Miranda & Morais (2019)	AR39-Oreck (2016)
AE4-Silva, Sousa & Silva (2021)	AR17-Miyata & Maia (2021)	AR41-Bojulaia & Pleasants (2021)
AE5-Luna (2016)	AR18-Monteiro, Braga & Nakano (2013)	AR42-Çelik & Tümen Akyildiz (2021)
AE6-Garcia & Machado (2020)	AR19-Morais & Miranda (2021)	AR43-Ghabanchi & Al-Khafaji (2019)
AE7-Araújo e Silva; Gontijo (2016)	AR20-Oliveira & Lima (2017)	AR44-Raba & Harzallah (2018)
AE8-Moreira (2020)	AR21-Oliveira & Cavalcante (2015)	AR45-Huang, Chi-Kin Lee & Yang (2019)
AE9-Santos (2016)	AR22-Porto (2021)	AR46-Huang, Sun & Wang (2022)
AE10-Silva, Negreiros & Rocha (2013)	AR23-Quintella & Vitaliano (2016)	AR47-Morralo et al. (2020)
AE11 -Ventura-Acosta, Rodríguez-Rodríguez & Gimeno-Nieves (2020)	AR24-Rocha (2021)	AR48-Nechifor & Purcaru (2016)
AR1-Anache & Fernandes (2015)	AR25-Rosa & Lindner (2020)	AR49-Dikici (2014)
AR2-Hofstaetter (2022)	AR26-Silva & Lima (2020)	AR50-Şorgo (2012)
AR3-Aquino & Cunha (2015)	AR27-Vieira & Coimbra (2020)	AR51-Sung & Vong (2021)
AR4-Guevara & Valdés (2020)	AR28-Zanella (2015)	AR52-Hunter & Emery (2015)
AR5-Câmara & Mascarenhas (2023)	AR29-Moya (2019)	AR53-Tripon (2021)

AR6-Maia & Vieira (2017)	AR30-Carrillo, Medina & Sosa (2019)	CL1-Amante & Silva (2020)
AR7-Coimbra & Vieira (2021)	AR31-Pita, Solano & Aguilar (2019)	CL2-Fernandes (2017)
AR8-Barros & Passos (2018)	AR32-Blanquiz & Villalobos (2018)	CL3-Rodrigues & Kotz (2023)
AR9-Araújo et al. (2021)	AR33- Navarro (2017)	CL4-Da Rocha (2019)
AR10-Reis et al. (2021)	AR34- Padrón (2019)	CL5-Sánchez Llorens (2022)
AR11-Dias, Morais & Braga (2017)	AR35-Gómez, Patiño & Delgado (2018)	CL6-Tarrio (2014)
AR12-Dmitrichenkova et al. (2021)	AR36-Cedeño, Meza & Valencia (2021)	
AR13-Maia & Coimbra (2017)	AR37-Al-Dababneh & Al-Zboon (2017)	

Source: The authors (2024).

The publications received specific codes to facilitate their identification: AR for journal articles, AE for conference proceedings articles, and CL for book chapters. For illustration, the code AR15 refers to the fifteenth journal article in the corpus. Extracted excerpts from the texts were also coded; for example, the code CL2.3 indicates that the third excerpt from the second book chapter in the corpus was used for composing the reflection.

The qualitative analysis of the excerpts was inspired by Bardin's Content Analysis (2016), based on three chronological stages: pre-analysis (the organization phase proper), material exploration (the coding, decomposition, or enumeration phase of excerpts deemed significant to the established research questions), and treatment of results, inference, and interpretation (processing raw data to make them meaningful and valid).

Analysis

During the extraction of significant excerpts from the corpus of this research, several points of attention began to emerge, the first being the focus of the investigations, that is, whether they were centered on the teacher, the student, or both. This evaluation served as a content control mechanism, since the intended focus was on the teacher, although the student could also be incorporated when relevant. It was also noted that, although the selected time frame spanned the last ten years, covering January 2013 to May 2023, the actual publications ranged from 2015 to 2023. Furthermore, empirical studies were the most common methodological approach, adopting formats such as case studies, narrative inquiry, and participant observation.

Regarding research approaches, all possibilities were included: purely qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-method studies. Nevertheless, a clear emphasis on qualitative research was observed, perhaps reflecting a prevailing trend in the investigation of creativity within the educational context.

In terms of publication concentration, there was an increase from 2020 onward, indicating a growing interest in or relevance of the topic in recent years. Additionally, many publications featured multiple authors, suggesting a trend toward collaborative research efforts. The most frequently cited authors were Maia, Vieira, and Coimbra.¹¹

The data reveals an interesting mosaic of investigations into teaching creativity, reflecting its nuances and complexities. Once again, this aspect allows us to revisit a fundamental point in the field, as noted by Martínez (2002, p. 190), who states that “sometimes, the simplicity and trivialization of the very concept [of creativity] become barriers to effective work aimed at achieving truly meaningful results.”

In line with Martínez's (2002) perspective, it was found that most of the studies presented at least a minimal definition of creativity, either by referencing classical authors or by offering their own understandings, whether explicitly stated or scattered throughout the text. Figure 1 illustrates which publications do or do not present an understanding of creativity in their discussions, indicating progress in relation to Martínez's warning and allowing, subsequently, for the research questions of this study to be addressed.

Continuing the description of the publications, it was observed that many studies do not focus on a specific subject area but rather address the teacher's practice in general. This observation points to two demands: first, for studies on teaching creativity in a broad sense, into which this review fits, and second, for studies that are interrelated with teachers' specific fields of practice (see Figure 2).

Among the subject areas identified, as shown in Figure 2, Pedagogy was the most prominent, followed by Arts or Visual Arts. There were also representations in Mathematics, Music Education, Foreign Languages, Natural Sciences, Biological Sciences, Portuguese Language, Social Sciences, Philosophy, Literature, English, Biology, and Interdisciplinary areas, such as Biology, Chemistry, Geography, and Portuguese Language. Some fields, such as English/Mathematics and Interdisciplinary, suggest a combination of subject areas within certain publications.

¹¹ Maria Vitória Campos Mamede Maia, Camila Nagem Marques Vieira e Silvia Gabrielle Braz Coimbra.

Figure 1 – Network of publications with and without evidence of a concept of creativity.

Source: The authors (2024) using CmapTools.

Figure 2 – Network of publications and their fields of knowledge.

Source: The authors (2024) using CmapTools.

Regarding the countries represented, Brazil had the highest number of publications, followed by Spain, Portugal, the United States, and China. In Latin America, aside from Brazil, notable contributions came from Colombia, Cuba, Venezuela, Mexico, Argentina/Uruguay, and the Dominican Republic. In the Middle East and Asia, countries such as Jordan, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, Iraq, Palestine, and the Philippines were also represented. In the European context, in addition to Portugal and Spain, there were contributions from Russia, Slovenia, and Romania. Tasmania, an island south of Australia, also appeared on the list, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Network of publications and the countries involved.

Source: The authors (2024) using CmapTools.

Taking a qualitative approach, one of the strategies used in this study was to examine the concepts of teaching creativity through the lens of practices and strategies aimed at fostering creativity. In addition, we considered records of the challenges and conditions related to creativity within the pedagogical context.

The *a priori* categories were intentionally aligned with the supporting research questions and organically connected to the *a posteriori* category, considering that reflecting on the concepts of teaching creativity involves defining and understanding what it means to be a creative teacher, by exploring different definitions and approaches. The development of the *a priori* categories, defined throughout the reading process and prior to the analysis of the significant excerpts, allowed us to establish the main fields of interest. As a result, “Theories and Foundations of Creative Teaching” and “Practices and Instruments of Creative Teaching” emerged and were consolidated. On the other hand, these categories revealed specificities that gave rise to the first four *a posteriori* subcategories, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – A priori and a posteriori categories

A priori categories	A posteriori categories	
Theories and Foundations of Creative Teaching	General Concepts of Creativity	Creative Thinking
		The Relevance of Creativity
	Creativity in the Educational Context	Creativity in Contemporary Education
		Creativity in Teacher Training and Practice
Practices and Tools of Creative Teaching	Environment and Tools for Educational Creativity	Challenges of Creativity in Teaching Practice
		Environment and Context in Promoting Creativity
	Assessment in Creative Teaching Practice	Use of Technology and Media in Creative Teaching and Learning
		Assessment and Teaching Creativity

Source: The authors (2024).

From the four aforementioned subcategories, other new groupings emerged. For example, when reflecting on “General Concepts of Creativity,” the themes of “Creative Thinking” and the “Relevance of Creativity” were frequently addressed. When focusing on “Creativity in the Educational Context,” the following themes were highlighted: “Creativity in Contemporary Education,” “Creativity in Teacher Training and Practice,” and “Challenges of Creativity in Teaching Practice.”

The two subcategories derived from “Practices and Tools of Creative Teaching” concerned the practical aspects of “Environment and Tools for Educational Creativity” and “Assessment in Creative Teaching Practice.” From the first subcategory, two related topics emerged: “Environment and Context in Promoting Creativity” and “Use of Technology and Media in Creative Teaching and Learning.” From the second, the theme “Assessment and Teaching Creativity” was derived.

- Category 1 – Theories and Foundations of Creative Teaching

In this first category, we explore elements related to the theories and foundations of creative teaching addressed in the analyzed material. To that end, topics such as creative thinking and the relevance of creativity are discussed in general terms, as well as creativity in the educational context from the perspective of contemporary education, including teacher training, professional practice, and the challenges faced in teaching.

General Concepts of Creativity

When investigating creativity, various theories and discussions emerge and are shown to be constantly evolving. One example of this is the transition from an approach centered on individual creative development to a multivariate perspective (Amabile, 1996). Thus, the first category addresses the general concepts of creativity and its integration into the educational debate.

Creative thinking arises from the reflection that students, throughout their educational journeys, may develop a tendency to quickly accept facts and information without proper critical analysis. It is the educator's role to ensure that they are encouraged to question and verify the information presented, thereby developing critical and creative thinking.

As identified in AR9.2, creative thinking, described as a dynamic process that oscillates between convergent and divergent thinking, is driven by both innate and developed abilities. However, the full realization of this creative potential faces several practical challenges in the classroom environment, which means that traditional teaching methods, those disconnected from students' realities, must be rethought and replaced by more relevant and engaging methods (AR26.3), establishing the relevance of creativity in the educational context.

The relevance of creativity comes with the understanding that, historically, the ability to think and create in original ways has laid the foundation for innovation, discovery, and cultural evolution. Nevertheless, the definition of creativity and what it truly means to be creative has been the subject of study and debate. Araújo e Silva and Gontijo (2016) indicate that a crucial aspect in the conceptualization of creativity is recognizing that it is intrinsically linked to novelty and usefulness (AE7.2).

At its core, creativity can be defined as a process in which something new and original is produced seemingly out of nothing (AE4.3). The ability to be creative translates into the capacity to make sense of the world around us, reworking the reality we live in (AR20.1). On the other hand, CL5.1 highlights that although creative capacity is inherent to the human being, it was long viewed as a myth, and only in the last century [20th century] was it recognized and defined as the ability to find multiple solutions to a single problem.

In contemporary society, creativity transcends restricted contexts, such as those of geniuses, and is also seen as the ability to solve everyday problems, making it a significant human value (AE2.1). Furthermore, according to Rank, Pace e Frese (2004) and Runco et al. (2016), "Creativity is not static," and can be seen as both a dynamic and unstable parameter (AR12.1). This implies that creativity can evolve and adapt over time and in different situations. This notion of adaptability is reinforced by AR6.2, which associates creativity with flexibility, allowing individuals to adjust to a constantly changing world.

According to AR28.1, Vygotsky also contributed to the understanding of creativity. From the Vygotskian perspective, the creative individual operates through imagination, appropriation, modification, and recombination of what already exists, with the goal of producing something new. This ability to reimagine and restructure existing ideas in order to create innovative solutions is fundamental to the definition of creativity. Moreover, creativity manifests whenever an original solution is formulated for a problem (AR30.1), and an individual is considered creative when they use different approaches in the conception of new ideas (AR30.2). A creative person is someone who can unify their thinking self with their pre-thinking self, reflecting a harmony between introspection and expression (AR29.1). In this way, contemporary education and the development of creativity are intertwined, and this *status* will be the focus of the next subcategory.

Creativity in the Educational Context

Creativity plays a fundamental role in the educational landscape, facing obstacles and seeking ways to address them. That said, this subcategory explores the importance of creativity in contemporary education, highlighting its role in teacher training and practice, as well as the challenges faced when incorporating creativity into pedagogical approaches.

Creativity in contemporary education is connected to the current educational scenario. As discussed in AR4.2, it faces the challenge of increasing student population density and the diversity inherent in it. This partial recognition of diversity brings the difficulty of addressing the individual differences among students. In this context, AR32.2 emphasizes the importance of building a creative teaching practice capable of valuing and embracing such diversity, becoming a vital link for pedagogical effectiveness.

The relevance of creativity in education is also justified to sharpen the desire to learn, reflect, critique, and transform (AE7.3). The studies discussed so far converge in emphasizing the pertinence of creativity in the pedagogical environment. According to an excerpt from AE10.1, creativity in teaching aims to motivate students to reflect on their attempts when engaging in school activities. This not only strengthens the bonds between teachers and students, but also highlights the subjectivity and originality of individuals in formation.

By identifying the skills of each participant in the educational process, particularly the teacher, we also build opportunities that respond to the pedagogical demands that emerge in everyday interactional environments. This enables students to investigate, discover, and express themselves in diverse ways, requiring educators to have a deep understanding of the aesthetic characteristics of the teaching experience (AR34.1, AR39.1).

The researchers whose publications compose our analysis *corpus*, even if briefly, underline what we refer to as a “pedagogical intentionality” toward and with creativity. That is, it arises from distinct yet interrelated movements, as explained by Beghetto (2017, p. 549), when he states that “creative teaching, like all forms of teaching, is a polymorphic act. It can take multiple forms and serve different pedagogical purposes.” Accordingly, three forms of creative teaching ¹²emerge: teaching about creativity, teaching for creativity, and teaching with creativity, each with different pedagogical goals and knowledge bases (Beghetto, 2017).

¹² In short, teaching “about” creativity aims to promote understanding of the creative phenomenon and its field of study; teaching “for” creativity seeks to develop students’ creativity; and teaching “with” creativity aims to teach a subject.

Reflecting on creativity in contemporary education leads us to the teacher, who must not only understand what it means to be creative but also know how to articulate that creativity using strategies and techniques that ensure learning success (AR36.1). However, this does not have to be done alone, as teaching practice is strongly embedded in structural conditions, more so than in the configuration or design of a system, for example, educational policies, availability of continuing education, safe and equipped environments, among others; and structural conditions, which refer to more fundamental and immutable aspects of a system or context, such as the value placed on the teaching profession, school culture, and the social and geographic conditions of the community in which the school is located.

The subcategory *creativity in teacher training and practice*, previously related to the conditions that foster creativity in education, reveals that promoting creativity in the classroom is not a task free of challenges, and that several factors may limit its expression. This may be the main reason to train or become a creative teacher. Authors suggest that teachers should have an established understanding of what creativity means to them and how it can be integrated into pedagogical practice (AR33.1), which implies recognizing and harnessing the potential of all those involved in the educational process, particularly the teachers themselves (AR33.1, AR34.1).

We have observed that both initial and continuing teacher education already demand creativity, requiring educators to develop active listening skills, openness to otherness, and a broad understanding of observable concepts and phenomena in the world (AR24.1, AR1.2). In this sense, and regarding the teaching role, teacher training is essentially a call for creative expression and, as indicated in AR18.1, becomes more than simply being an information facilitator.

The teacher's experience with their own creative process is also fundamental for developing empathy with students and adapting instruction to ensure the effectiveness of applied techniques (AR40.2, AR36.1). Therefore, it is strategic for teachers to direct their instructional focus toward enhancing creativity (AR41.1), and studies already indicate that some teachers find ways to overcome challenges in pedagogical practice, creating quality teaching and learning spaces (AR27.1), in which teacher self-evaluation and expectations regarding creativity are part of the process (AR45.1).

The definition of a teacher who fosters creativity, as described by Cropley (1997), cited in AR49.1, reinforces this need for self-awareness and flexibility. Such a teacher adopts a cooperative and integrative teaching style that adapts to and responds to the needs and suggestions of students, varying according to the demographic characteristics of the target audience. A creative teacher is one who promotes environments where the freedom to create is valued. These spaces must be flexible, autonomous, and conducive to enabling everyone to experience authorship (AR27.1).

According to AE11.1, a creative teacher, throughout the educational process, must remain attuned to technological and scientific advancements and be able to adapt to new methodologies. Furthermore, in order to foster an environment conducive to creativity, it is essential that teachers possess traits such as imagination, flexibility, and integration, as highlighted in AE11.2. That is, educators should be capable of combining established and innovative methods, connecting different fields of knowledge, and, above all, valuing creativity both in their own practice and in that of their students.

Various aspects contribute to understanding the nature of teacher creativity, and AR6.1 also highlights flexibility as an intrinsic feature of this competence, enabling educators to handle various educational situations and demands. In addition, according to AR6.3 and AR6.4, creativity functions as a mobilizing tool in teaching practice, with its origins and development intertwined within the space of interaction with students.

As noted in AR5.3, a good teacher must be capable of sparking curiosity and creativity in students. However, this teaching practice involves openness to new experiences, breaking with existing paradigms (AR11.2), and continuous immersion in the teaching process (AR32.1), constantly seeking new ways to teach and learn (AR39.2, AR43.1). That said, to effectively foster creativity, educators must prioritize the development of students' cognitive independence, and trust in human potential and innate abilities is a prerequisite for this process (AR31.1).

Within this category, it was observed that researchers have recognized education as one of the cornerstones of individual development, and creativity emerges as a key element in this process. Educating for creativity means shaping individuals capable of facing challenges and driving meaningful changes in society by fostering critical, reflective, and original thinking (AE1.1). In this sense, looking ahead, one of the most valued skills of

the 21st century is creativity. Educators around the world are exploring strategies to promote disciplinary competencies and foster this skill (AR53.1). However, this paradigm shift will not occur without facing challenges—an issue we address in the final subcategory related to creativity in the educational context, namely, the challenges of *creativity in teaching practice*.

The *challenges of creativity in teaching practice* are accompanied by the awareness that, although the importance of creativity is recognized among educators, some obstacles remain in its implementation. Among them is the need to move beyond teacher-centered instruction focused solely on transmitting information (AR26.1, AR47.1). Consequently, incorporating creativity into educational practice becomes essential so that educators can go beyond a linear transmission of knowledge (as if that were even possible) and instead focus on the student's holistic development (AE2.2).

The challenges associated with the pedagogical work environment, including insecurities and various forms of violence, such as verbal abuse, property damage, and other forms of symbolic violence, as highlighted in AR7.1, can significantly compromise a teacher's creative capacity. The depletion of this capacity, due to excessive work demands, calls for a reinvention of both the teacher's profile and the school culture. This need becomes especially evident in institutions where collective planning proves ineffective, failing to meet its intended goals, such as the sharing of effective practices and ongoing professional development (AR7.2, AR21.3, AR25.1).

Additionally, a recurring concern is that schools sometimes resist innovation, and aspects such as class size and management may restrict creative thinking (AR44.1). In this regard, a study mentioned in excerpt AR38.1 reveals divergent views on the ideal environment to promote creativity. While school administrators believe that teacher training is key to fostering creativity, teachers point to well-equipped classrooms with advanced technologies as the best path forward. However, the authors did not detail what such environments would look like. Both groups, however, agree that reducing class sizes and curriculum content, as well as fostering family cooperation and promoting extracurricular activities, would benefit creative development. While we agree with the first point, we do not necessarily concur with the second.

School culture ¹³Plays a fundamental role in fostering creativity. In this context, AR7.3 and AR8.1 emphasize the need for a welcoming and supportive environment and the transformation of the educational space through pedagogical practices that promote creativity. Furthermore, AR8.2 and AR8.3 reaffirm the importance of re-signifying and reconstructing knowledge in the school context through a sensitive listening approach, something aligned with Gardner (2001), who argues that optimal creative development requires environments rich in discovery. Such environments must minimize prohibitions and barriers to free exploration. Gardner (2001) stresses the importance of specific stimuli and an environment that nurtures creativity, claiming that creativity results from the development of domain-specific intelligences (AR23.1, AR23.2).

As highlighted in AR27.3, to subvert obsolete practices and be truly creative, teachers must reflect on their pedagogical approaches, shaping themselves into empowered and active professionals. This new posture may involve a multifaceted approach to learning, as well as a strong emphasis on communication and continuous collaboration as central pillars of creative teaching and teaching for creativity (AR39.1, AR47.1).

In the teaching profession, the combination of academic and administrative tasks can limit the time available for genuinely creative planning. This restriction, in turn, may act as a barrier to creative expression within the pedagogical context. A reflection of this is the structuring of school time, which often imposes rigid patterns of action and reflection, thereby restricting creativity in the educational space, as noted in AR1.3 and AR4.1.

Time-related challenges in the teaching and learning process can significantly impact teachers' actions, as there may not be sufficient time to explore a concept in depth. As a result, the chosen methodology may inadvertently restrict students' autonomous thinking, as pointed out in AE7.4. Furthermore, insufficient understanding of the content by the teacher, often due to a lack of time for lesson preparation, can lead to a more automated teaching approach, depriving it of creativity, as mentioned in AE7.5. Therefore,

¹³ "Both implicitly and explicitly, a school's culture is conveyed to young people every day and in many ways: through the structure and content of the curriculum; in the relationships between teachers and students; in the methods and criteria of assessment; in the way the school is managed and, in its connections, — or lack thereof — with the broader community.". NACCCE Report – *National Advisory Committee on Creative and Cultural Education* – 1999, p. 112.

such challenges act as constraints on the development of creativity and teaching for creativity. However, creative teachers and their practices and tools do emerge, and these will be the focus of the next category.

- Category 2 – Practices and Tools for Creative Teaching

In this second category, we explore elements that contribute to the promotion of creativity in the educational environment. From this interest, two central themes emerge: the environment and tools for creativity, which include discussions on the settings and contexts that foster creativity, as well as the strategic use of technology and media in creative teaching and learning, and assessment in creative teaching practice, highlighting how evaluation can be integrated into a creative pedagogical approach.

The environment and context for promoting creativity: Creativity is a multifaceted aspect of human personality that can be significantly influenced by the environment and context in which the individual is situated. In the educational setting, in particular, the environment plays a strategic role in either promoting or inhibiting the creative expression of those involved. As emphasized by Alencar and Formiga Sobrinho (2017) and Fleith and Morais (2017), creating an environment that stimulates students' curiosity, autonomy, and self-confidence is essential for fostering creativity (AR19.2).

Valuing and encouraging the expression of ideas, accepting differing viewpoints, and flexibility in perspectives can help make the educational environment conducive to the manifestation of creative attitudes and outcomes. Moreover, psychological safety in the classroom is crucial, a space where students feel comfortable taking risks and making mistakes, since this perception of safety fosters autonomy, critical thinking, and participation overall (AR19.3).

The nature of the content covered, and the teaching strategies employed by educators also have a direct impact on the promotion of a creative environment and context. Thus, routine should be avoided and diversity reinforced, along with alignment to students' interests. Otherwise, environments with excessive demands, whether physical or emotional, may result in a depletion of the individual's creative capacity (AR7.2). In such situations, the focus shifts from innovation and creative expression to mere survival.

Considering the influence of the environment and context on promoting creativity, several factors are critical, from the educator's posture to classroom infrastructure conditions. Additionally, the literature emphasizes the importance of building a climate of trust in the classroom, which allows students greater autonomy in choosing their learning process, encompassing both content and methodology (CL6.4). This approach appears to be key to generating a creative environment in the educational context, which has also become increasingly technological.

The intensive, extensive, and combined use of media has become a cornerstone of the contemporary educational landscape. This brings forth the discussion on *technology and media in teaching and learning*. Multimodal languages, including written, auditory, visual, audiovisual, hypermedia, and playful aspects, have been widely implemented in pedagogical practices, blending in-person activities with the use of apps for problem-solving.

The situation described above can be observed in the growing use of social media, meme creation, graphs, videos, games, and other resources (AE3.1). In this way, digital integration goes beyond the realm of new creations, blending with traditional images and texts, highlighting an inevitable fusion in contemporary times and enriching the creative process of various professionals, including educators (AE8.1).

It is important to note that the incorporation of these technologies is not limited to curriculum components traditionally associated with technology. In other areas, such as mathematics, technological integration can enhance learning, especially when educators use Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) creatively (AE9.1). In this context, teacher creativity is also essential in defining instructional strategies that involve digital technologies, going beyond a mere transposition of traditional teaching, as previously defined, into technology-rich environments (AR34.2). However, alongside new topics, such as the use of digital technologies, there are also long-standing debates, for instance, learning assessment, which also emerged during the research and forms the final subcategory identified in this study.

Creativity requires innovative teaching practices, purposeful planning, and a deep understanding of the concept. Teaching with and for creativity demands creativity itself, but assessing creativity also requires an equally creative¹⁴ Approach. This is the focus of the

¹⁴ Inspired by "Talking about creativity requires creativity. Doing with creativity requires even more creativity."
— Ana P. Martins (Creativity in Mathematical Activity, 2020).

final subcategory. That said, *assessment and teacher creativity* can form a pedagogical resource which, when used effectively, enhances the creative teaching and learning process. As mentioned in CL1.2, active pedagogy ¹⁵Plays a key role in this context. Through it, students, when responding to stimuli, are encouraged to solve problems in collaboration with peers, for example, by discussing solutions, expanding their knowledge, and thus becoming more creative themselves (AR5.2, AR9.1, AR9.4).

Regarding pedagogical planning and assessment, it is important to highlight the essential task of designing and developing creative tasks and tasks for creativity, tailoring them to the characteristics and contexts in which students are situated. This also includes considering their physical and psychological traits, such as chronological age, which allows for the gradual expansion of their abilities (AE4.4, AR3.1, AR35.1). This student-centered pedagogical approach becomes prevalent when students are involved in creative situations and regarded as active participants in the daily school routine, including assessment processes (AR42.1, AR50.2).

The figure of the innovative teacher, committed to creativity and who views education as a tool for transformation, is central in this context (AR16.1). Assessment is a powerful instrument in pedagogical practice. The importance of intentional planning, which considers students' prior knowledge and what they still need to learn, is fundamental (AE7.7). However, there is a noticeable trend that assessment, particularly when poorly applied, can restrict creativity and playful approaches in education (AR13.1). Formative assessment, in contrast, takes into account each student's individuality and previous learning, emphasizing constant feedback to promote more effective learning (AR14.2).

The assessment of creativity as a teaching practice has not yet stood out in research from the past decade. Nonetheless, it already indicates that education with and for creativity must, essentially, recognize and foster creativity in each student. This also implies granting pedagogical autonomy, providing material resources to develop innovative teaching materials, and creating engaging lessons, elements that can also be considered

¹⁵ We are, therefore, advocates of this type of active pedagogy, in which students, responding to a stimulus, are called upon to solve problems through interaction with others and, in doing so, discuss possible solutions, expand their knowledge, and become more creative (Amante; Silva, 2020, p. 88).

part of teacher creativity (AR4.3, AR9.5, AR48.2). However, not everything is convergent, as will be addressed in the final section.

Convergences, Divergences, and Perceptions

During this Systematic Literature Review (SLR), a diversity of perspectives, methods, and interpretations was observed. However, some convergences and divergences emerged, which are relevant to the reflections previously presented and open up new possibilities for further research in this field. Starting with the question: What are the main convergences and divergences regarding the concepts of teacher creativity found in these studies? (SQ2), it became evident that there is a prevailing tendency to acknowledge the importance of creativity in the teaching and learning context. Many excerpts emphasize creativity as essential to education, both generally and within specific disciplines, indicating that it is crucial to forming critical, reflective, and original individuals (AE1.1, AE2.1, AE2.2, AE7.3, AE10.1, AR5.1, AR9.3, AR19.1, AR24.1).

In addition to recognizing the value of creative competence itself, there is also a strong convergence concerning the role of the teacher, which must be active and encouraging of students' curiosity and creative expression (AE4.1, AE4.2, AE6.1, AR15.1, AR15.2, AR15.3, AR19.1, CL3.1, CL4.1, AR31.3, AR31.4, AR33.1). Thus, the creative teacher profile outlined by the research in this review is one of autonomy, flexibility, adaptability, and the ability to create approaches that meet students' needs (AR6.2, AR26.1, AR27.1, AR27.3, AR31.5, AR34.1, AR36.1, AR40.2, AR50.1).

According to the authors, creative teachers must also be capable of recognizing and valuing this competence in their students, treating their ideas and suggestions with respect (AR31.4, AR48.2, AR49.1). However, these qualities are not only expected of teachers; the studies also emphasize that such a paradigm shift requires professional development, which must be ongoing and focused on creativity (AR24.1, CL4.1, AR27.3, AR33.1, AR50.1).

While the convergences point to a scenario strongly focused on teacher agency, giving the impression that the teacher acts alone, disconnected from a broader educational system that should also share responsibility for pedagogical practices, the divergences begin with the very definition of creativity. While some studies define creativity as the

ability to solve everyday problems (AE2.1) or create something seemingly from nothing (AE4.3), others view it as a skill to reinterpret and understand reality (AR20.1) or as a means to generate new knowledge and solutions (AR31.3).

Another divergence lies in the methods suggested to foster creativity. Some proposals involve the use of the arts (AR39.1), the creation of enjoyable learning experiences (AE5.1), or even more structured and planned approaches (AE11.2). Thus, beyond understanding theoretical concepts of creativity, teachers need to grasp how this competence relates to their disciplinary area, and this kind of training could help address questions such as: Is it more appropriate to approach creativity in a differentiated and individual way (AR48.3) or by emphasizing collaboration and communication with others (AR47.1)?

One study revealed that teachers' creative personalities and beliefs about creativity are crucial and aligned with how they perceive and implement it in their pedagogical practices (AR37.1). This suggests that, to cultivate creative educational environments, it is essential to recognize and nurture the creativity of educators themselves. AR32.3 supports this idea by highlighting teacher education as a key starting point.

Another relevant aspect emerges when we consider the continuous professional development of teachers. When well-structured, professional development experiences seem to strengthen teachers' creativity, encouraging them to take risks and find personal meaning in the teaching and learning process (AR39.2). This approach, focused on professional development, can thus have a profound impact on daily teaching practice. Additionally, the emergence of new digital technologies and pedagogical methodologies, such as project-based learning, offers promising avenues for the promotion of creativity (AR53.1).

Recent studies by Chmelárová, Pasiarb, and Vargová (2020), and by Akhtar and Kartika (2020), show that such methods, alongside other factors such as a creative climate and emotional intelligence, can be decisive in developing students' creativity. As a result, we find that these publications, beyond answering the proposed research questions, also provided several insights for continuing this research or conducting new research on the topic of teacher creativity.

The studies highlight the relevance of creativity not only as an intrinsic ability, but also as an essential 21st-century skill (AR53.1). The implementation of pedagogical strategies that foster creativity has therefore become an urgent demand. In terms of organizing the information and reflections on teachers' attitudes within their circles of influence, a conceptual framework was established, Table 3, which will serve as a foundation for this study's conclusion and for answering the questions initially posed.

The seven circles of influence and thirty-five teaching attitudes that emerged from the systematization and reflections based on the studies included in this systematic literature review present a comprehensive view of the attitudes and practices that educators can adopt to positively influence teaching and learning with and for creativity, emphasizing innovation in teaching practices, with diverse methods, and the redefinition of the teacher's role in order to create a dynamic learning environment.

Table 3 – Teaching attitudes and their circles of influence

Circles of influence	Teaching attitudes
Regarding teaching and pedagogical approaches	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adopt an intentional and creative pedagogical approach, combined with continuous reflection on the methods used. 2. Diversify teaching methods and formats to encourage greater student activity and engagement. 3. Implement active pedagogy to foster problem-solving and collaboration among students. 4. Modernize and revitalize outdated teaching methods, making them more relevant and engaging. 5. Redefine the teacher's role for the 21st century, acting as a knowledge mediator.
Regarding student creativity and critical thinking	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Encourage students to question and verify information, developing critical and creative thinking. 2. Stimulate curiosity, autonomy, and self-confidence. 3. Engage in one's own creative teaching process. 4. Foster creativity through imagination, appropriation, modification, and recombination of existing ideas. 5. Recognize creativity as the ability to find multiple solutions to a single problem.
Regarding diversity and inclusion	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acknowledge student diversity and interests. 2. Value and accept divergent ideas. 3. Appreciate both convergent and divergent thinking.
Regarding the teacher-student relationship	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Awaken the desire to learn, reflect, critique, and transform. 2. Identify individual abilities to respond to pedagogical demands. 3. Motivate students to understand their efforts. 4. Foster a safe and curious environment, free from insecurity and violence. 5. Be explicit about what creativity is and how to integrate it into practice.
Regarding technology and modern methods	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Integrate digital tools with traditional content. 2. Enhance learning through digital technologies. 3. Use multimodal languages in pedagogical practices. 4. Use technologies and media critically and creatively.

Regarding student development and skills	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Foster students' cognitive independence. 2. Educate individuals capable of facing challenges and promoting change. 3. Reframe and reconstruct knowledge.
Regarding the educator's skills, characteristics, and attitudes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Be open to new experiences, break paradigms, and seek innovation. 2. Be aware of the challenges of assessment as a teaching and learning tool. 3. Avoid working in isolation. 4. Recognize the need for continuous professional development. 5. Possess qualities such as imagination, flexibility, integration, and appreciation of creativity. 6. Balance between inspiring creativity and presenting reality. 7. Practice active listening. 8. Promote a school culture essential to fostering creativity. 9. Be flexible and adaptable. 10. Value collaborative planning.

Source: The authors (2024).

They highlight the importance of developing creativity and critical thinking in students, promoting curiosity and autonomy, and emphasize the value of diversity and inclusion, the importance of a positive teacher-student relationship, the integration of technology in teaching, and the preparation of students for independence and for proposing and solving problems. Lastly, it focuses on the ongoing development of educators, valuing flexibility, collaboration, and innovation.

Final Considerations

What is the concept of teacher creativity? This was the central question of this systematic literature review (SLR), and to answer it, it was necessary to reflect on the theories, foundations, and tools of creative teaching. However, the research unfolded into more specific topics. When the focus was on creativity in the educational context, themes such as creativity in contemporary education, in teacher training and practice, and its associated challenges emerged.

The most recent concept of teacher creativity identified in the studies analyzed in this SLR is that of Vieira and Coimbra (2020, p. 886), AR27, for whom it is "understood as the educator's ability to build spaces for themselves and their students where it is possible to experience the freedom to create and the authorship of thought." Here, the focus is on the teacher's identity; however, we understand that being a creative teacher is more than possessing a skill, it is being competent, since the very multiplicity of teaching practices requires a set of abilities to foster and promote creativity in teaching and learning spaces.

Vieira and Coimbra (2020, p. 886) continue the definition and state that being a creative teacher is, therefore, “to be capable of promoting teaching and learning spaces that are sufficiently good for everyone,” and they explain what this means: “It is to be flexible, autonomous, yet aware of one's dependencies. It is to engage with others, creating spaces where everyone can experience, in their own time and manner, the possibility of authorship. It is to care without suffocating, to guide without pruning.”

From the 70 publications, it was possible to outline attitudes, actions, or demands of a creative teacher, which encompassed teaching and pedagogical approaches, the promotion of student creativity and critical thinking, diversity and inclusion in the school environment, the teacher-student relationship, the characteristics and skills of creative educators, the use of creativity through technology and modern methods, and the development of students' cognitive independence.

We infer, then, that a teacher is capable of being creative when they recognize the appropriate level of technical and pedagogical knowledge for their teaching field, understand their own weaknesses and strengths, as well as those of their colleagues, administrators, and the school community, remain attentive to continuing education opportunities that align with their interests and needs, and feel confident during the processes of creating, developing, and presenting innovative approaches in their individual or collaborative teaching practices.

This educator diversifies teaching methods, adapting them to current demands. They understand that teaching is not merely the transmission of knowledge and embraces the role of a facilitator in the construction of learning. With a reflective posture, they invest in active pedagogy, valuing problem-posing and problem-solving, as well as student interaction. They adapt to the demands of the 21st century, showing themselves to be flexible and innovative.

In conclusion, we emphasize that diversity is seen as an asset by this teacher, who understands and values the individuality of each student, recognizing the uniqueness of their experiences and perspectives. In this sense, they encourage students to develop critical thinking by questioning and analyzing the information presented. They value creativity, using it as a pedagogical tool, and are unafraid to reinvent and adapt existing ideas. They view the classroom as a space that stimulates curiosity and autonomy, acting

as a catalyst for student creativity. In addition to being open to new experiences, they seek to break with outdated traditional paradigms in their teaching practices and, aware of the challenges of assessment, recognize their own pedagogical practices that align with the development of creativity and work toward building a school culture that fosters it.

Research on creativity in the educational context develops through distinct, albeit interconnected, pathways that require specific reflection. This study contributes to this field by highlighting complementary and interconnected aspects. The concept of teacher creativity, explored in this work, opens opportunities for future research. Among them, we highlight: the development of tools to assess creativity, teacher education about, with, and for creativity, and the study of teacher creativity in specific fields of practice, such as in mathematics education, for instance.

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